

Future Circular Collider

TECHNICAL REPORT

ELECTRON SOURCE AND PRE-INJECTOR DESIGN FOR THE FCC-EE

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ELECTRON SOURCE AND PRE-INJECTOR
DESIGN FOR THE FCC/EE

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1 Introduction

The European Strategy for particle physics recommended to study the implementation of a future circular collider at CERN called FCC [1]. A first version would function as a electron-positron collider (FCC-ee [2]) with the aim among others to study in detail the newly found Higg's bosson. This machine is one of the options for a new high energy accelerator at CERN. In a second phase the same tunnel could house a proton-proton collider. It would follow up the LHC (Large Hadron Collider) as the new high energy frontier of particle physics with collision energy of the order of 100 TeV. The injector chain of FCCee is currently studied by an international collaboration lead by PSI [3]. The injector chain consist of an electron pre-injector up to 200 MeV, an injector LINAC up to 1.5 GeV, a damping ring followed by a booster LINAC which accelerates the particles up to 6 GeV. At this energy level injection into the SPS synchrotron is envisaged followed by a booster ring and final injection into the collider ring. For positron production the 6 GeV electron are impinged on a target and captured by a 200 MeV positron pre-injector. Afterwards the positrons use the same injector chain as described for the electrons above [4]. This report describes the electron pre-injector of this injector chain. There are two main options for electron sources for such a machine, an RF-photo injector or a thermionic gun. The study comprises the source itself and a linear accelerator to accelerate the electrons up to 200 MeV.

This study will investigate the RF-photo injector option as an electron source and further acceleration up to energy $E = 200$ MeV, with a bunch charge up to 5 nC and emittance as low as possible but not higher than $100 \pi \cdot \text{mm} \cdot \text{mrad}$. The particle in cell tracking code ASTRA [5] has been used to simulate the injector including space charge effects and external electromagnetic fields.

2 Outline of the electron pre-injector

A generic outline for the pre-injector was generated to optimise its performance in simulations. The pre-injector starts with an RF-photogun, followed by accelerating structures (travelling wave cavities) up to an energy of $E = 200$ MeV, where the beam gets further accelerated by the injector linac up to 1.5 GeV. This injector linac will be a common accelerator for electrons and positrons. The transverse focusing will be likely done by solenoids in the pre-injector and then transition to quadrupoles in the injector linac.

For the time being as an realistic example of an accelerating structure for simulations, we are using the TWS-PSI-S-band used in the SwissFEL at the Paul Scherrer Institut described in [6]. The basic parameters are given in Tab. 1. This structure is an almost 4 m long classic travelling wave structure. Two or three of this structures would be needed to accelerate the beam to about 200 MeV depending on the gradient used. It might turn out during the injector simulations that a different accelerating structure can obtain better results or would be more economical but the above mentioned structures is certainly a good starting point.

The source itself is comprised of an RF-gun and focusing solenoids, one around the RF-gun and a bucking coil. The reason behind the bucking coil is to cancel

Figure 1: Basic photo-injector layout with one solenoid configuration and with the most crucial optimisation parameters indicated

Parameter	Value
Operating frequency	2998.8 MHz
Phase advance per cell	$2\pi/3$
Total number of cells	120+2
Accelerating gradient	20 - 30 MV/m
Maximum pulse repetition frequency	100 Hz

Table 1: Main paramatres of the SwissFEL S-band TWS

the magnetic field on the cathode surface to avoid emittance growth at very low energies. The RF-gun is again taken from SwissFEL at PSI for consistency and is described in [7], in Tab. 5 are given only the main parameters.

Parameter	Value
Operating frequency	2998.8 MHz
Total number of cells	2.5
Accelerating gradient	100 - 120 MV/m
mode separation	≥ 15 MHz

Table 2: Main paramatres of the SwissFEL RF-gun

The electromagnetic fields used in the simulation for acceleration and for focusing around the gun are shown in Fig. 2,3,4.

3 Required beam parameters at the end of the pre-injector

Here we list current requirements for the beam parameters at the end of the injector. Since the project is at the beginning, some specifications are still subject to modification. The specifications described in the following are the working hypothesis for this study.

The final energy of the pre-injector was fixed to 200 MeV. At this energy the

Figure 2: *Longitudinal electrical field E_z along the z -axes of the RF-gun*

space charge effects are negligible and the longitudinal phase space is stable. From this energy on the simulations for the following linacs can assume fully relativistic particles and therefore use different simulation tools. The energy of the pre-injector could be changed if it turns out to be advantages. One argument to choose this energy could be the transition from solenoid focusing to quadruple based focusing which could lead to emittance growth and typically determines the necessary aperture of the accelerating structures. This question will be studied with the following injector linac. For time being the energy for positrons at the end of their capture linac is as well set to 200 MeV. Since the following linac needs to accelerate both species one should pick the same energy for both pre-injector linacs.

The beam size through out the pre-injector linac should be small, in the order of a few mm to avoid losses and emittance growth. The solenoid focusing strength needs to be chosen accordingly.

There are several configurations of the electron-positron injector complex in consideration which have different requirements in terms of transverse emittance. The positron production needs to include in any case a damping ring to fulfill the transverse acceptance requirements of the pre-injector ring (SPS) and to minimise losses. The acceptance of the SPS ring is $A_{SPS} = 40 \text{ mm mrad}$, therefore an excellent electron source and following linacs with little emittance growth is needed or a damping ring has to be used as well for the electrons within the injector complex. The positron production does not put big constraints on the emittance of the electron beam. Therefore the aim of the electron source study was to achieve an emittance

Figure 3: *Longitudinal magnetic field B_z along the z -axes of the beam line and its derivative $\Delta Br/dr$*

below 20 mm mrad in the case of a photo injector and below 100 mm mrad in the case of a thermionic gun. The later would require a damping ring.

The operating charge of a bunch of the FCC-ee will be $Q = 3.2$ nC for both particle species. Since the current scheme involves positron production by bombarding a target with electrons from our source to save cost by using the same linacs, we need to have a margin for the positron production. The initial proposals were counting with 50% conversion rate, which we now know is pessimistic. The first results from the positron productions studies indicate that a positron yield of the order of 1 might be possible. For this study we decided to use a maximum charge of $Q = 5$ nC for positron production and $Q = 3.4$ nC for electron production to keep some margin.

Since the bunch length doesn't change much in the accelerator, it is mainly dictated by the emission time of the laser pulse. The main restriction of the bunch length in the injector comes from the energy spread sampled along the acceleration. A reasonable goal for the bunch length when entering the main injector linac is between $\sigma_z = 1 - 2$ mm. If such a bunch length can't be reached naturally by the injector a bunch compressor can be used in-between the pre-injector and the main injector. The effect the bunch length has on the RF curvature induced energy spread is shown in Fig. 5 (see chapter 5). These are the upper limits of the bunch length, but because of the space charge, we need to count with large enough margin to achieve those energy spread values in reality.

Figure 4: *Longitudinal electrical field E_z along the z -axes of the Accelerating structure*

Finally we will aim for a reasonable shape of the transverse and longitudinal phase spaces. What is reasonable will be determined by the simulations of the main-injector.

The above mentioned main target beam parameters at the end of the pre-injector at 200 MeV are summarized in Tab 3.

	electrons for positrons	electrons only
Bunch charge	5.0 nC	3.4 nC
Emittance	< 100 mm mrad	< 20 mm mrad
Bunch length [FWHM]	15 ps	15 ps
Energy spread	< 1%	< 0.5%
Energy	200 MeV	200 MeV

Table 3: *Target parameters for the electron pre-injector at 200 MeV*

4 Choice of the cathode type and laser requirements

4.1 Cathode

There are different possibilities for the cathode material in photo injectors. The choice of cathode influences the type of laser required to illuminate the cathode.

The main parameters of the cathode that we need to take into account are the quantum efficiency, ablation threshold, vacuum requirements, the lifetime and charge extraction stability. Two main categories of materials are typically used: plain metals like copper and semiconductors like cesium telluride (Cs_2Te).

Pure metals, for example Cu, are very easy to use have a long lifetime and need not an extremely good vacuum. The downside is the typically relatively low quantum efficiency QE of the order of $QE \simeq 10^{-5}$. The response times of metal cathodes are very fast ($\tau \simeq 10$ fs). Copper is the most common used material since the rf-cavities are constructed out of it and no special effort is needed to have a copper cathode inside. Copper however has not a very high ablation threshold which limits the laser spot size depending on the charge needed. In the case of FCCee where high charge electron bunches are required this effect might limit the obtainable emittance.

The second category are semiconductors which can reach much higher quantum efficiencies. The QE can reach several percent ($QE \simeq 0.1$) which reduces the laser power needed to generate a certain charge and therefore allows for a smaller spot size on the cathode. It was found that the response time of Cs_2Te is slower than for copper ($\tau \simeq 500$ fs), which actually smoothens the emissions of the electrons and can have positive effects on the longitudinal charge distribution. The big disadvantage of such cathode is their limited lifetime and the stringent vacuum requirements with a pressure on the gun of the order of 10^{-11} mbar. In addition a load lock system is needed to load these sensitive cathodes into the rf gun under vacuum.

For the FCCee the choice between a metal or semiconductor cathode will be a trade off between charge stability, emittance and operational aspects of the injector. If a copper cathode can fulfill the charge requirements without getting damaged it would be the more stable and easier to handle solution. On the other hand CERN has a lot of experience with Cs_2Te cathode which would ease the laser requirements but complicates the operation since the QE is reducing during operation and cathodes need to be changed from time to time.

4.2 Laser

If an electromagnetic wave with enough intensity hits a solid, it vaporizes material from the solid's surface. If the electromagnetic wave is short (pulse length $< 1\mu\text{m}$) we call this phenomenon ablation. Since we are dealing with high intensity laser pulses tens of picoseconds long, we ought to investigate the possibility that the required laser pulse for the bunch creation is higher intensity than the ablation threshold.

From work of [8] we have some rough estimates of ablation threshold for two pulse durations; for 100 fs pulses the intensity threshold is around (lower estimate) 10^{13} W/cm², for 100 ns pulse the intensity required is around 10^8 W/cm². Our pulse duration is around $\tau \approx 10$ ps, which is somewhere in the middle, so we can take an estimate of ablation threshold to be around 10^{10} W/cm², being the lower estimate. Now we can calculate the order of magnitude of intensity, that we need to generate the required bunch charge of $Q = 5$ nC with an estimated spot size of $S \approx 2$ mm². Also we take into account two different cathode types, the semiconductor and metal. The power needed to produce the required charge can be calculated with the following formula and is summarized in Tab. 4.

$$P = h \frac{c}{\lambda \tau} \frac{Q}{eQE} \quad (1)$$

So we can clearly see that the semiconductor cathode won't be in any danger from ablation since the required intensity is more than four orders of magnitude below the threshold. The situation is substantially different for the metal cathode. Here we are less than one order of magnitude below, since our estimations were very rough, this will need further investigations to see if copper is still an viable option.

Parameters	semiconductor	metal
QE	0.1	10^{-4}
laser wavelength λ /nm	≈ 500	≈ 250
power P /kW	≈ 12.4	≈ 24700
intensity I /Wcm ⁻²	$\approx 6.2 \times 10^5$	$\approx 1.2 \times 10^9$

Table 4: *Parameters of different cathode types*

5 Beam simulation and optimization

The goal of the optimisation was to provide a beam with the correct energy and charge with the best possible emittance. The energy spread and bunch length are secondary parameters of our optimisation since in theory they could be still manipulated in the following linacs. There are many parameters that could be optimised in such an electron injector, regarding both the initial beam distribution and the geometry and parameters of the beam line. Trying to optimise them all at once would be far too excessive in terms of computational resources. We therefore concentrate on the parameters for which it is difficult to predict their effect on the beam or which show the biggest sensitivity on our goal parameters. Table 5 lists the parameters which are most important to optimise in order to obtain a high quality beam at the end of the injector. Other parameters could be considered as fine tuning which can be done at a later point of the optimisation.

First of all we need to address the issue of generating two different bunch charges for the two different purposes. First to generate a beam consisting of bunches of electrons for final physics collisions, secondly to generate higher charge electron bunches to impinge on a target to create positron bunches with the correct charge for the

Parameter
Initial beam size
Emission time (initial bunch length)
Accelerating gradient of RF-gun
Phase offset of the RF-gun
RF-gun solenoid magnetic field strength
Accelerating gradient of each TWS
Phase offset of each TWS
TWS solenoids magnetic field strength
Position of TWS

Table 5: *Parameters most suitable for optimisation*

collider. The nominal charge for the electron bunch is, as listed above, 3.4 nC. For this study we used a bunch charge of 5.0 nC for positron production assuming that the positron yield will be sufficient to obtain positron bunches with 3.4 nC at the entrance of the collider requiring a minimum yield of 0.7. Since it would be desirable to be able to switch in the injector between these two bunch charges quickly the goal is to preserve the setting of the beam line elements as much as possible in particular the geometry and the magnetic elements. We therefore propose to change the initial laser spot size on the cathode in order to keep a similar charge density which would result in similar space charge forces.

For optimisation, we first need to define the figure of merit which we want to either minimize or maximize. For us there are two most important characteristics to consider, transverse emittance and energy spread. As will be explained below, the initial energy spread is determined by the emission time of the laser which sets the initial bunch length. Which means we can chose the energy spread we want to achieve and set the laser pulse length accordingly. In conclusion by optimisation we mean minimizing the emittance with a pre-defined energy spread.

5.1 Initial bunch characteristics

When we optimise for the geometrical properties of the beam, firstly we need to decide, what distribution of particles to use. Since we are using photo-effect to generate free electrons, the distribution of the electrons will be almost the same as the distribution of the power in the laser pulse. The most basic approach is to consider only Gaussian distribution in all three spatial direction while better emittances are typically obtained with uniform distributions. A typical laser will have a natural distribution somewhat in between a uniform and a pure Gaussian therefore we will use both theoretical distributions in our simulations to cover the extreme cases. Uniform distribution can be generated from a laser in the transverse plan by using an aperture to cut the tails. In the longitudinal direction plateau distributions have been approximated by longitudinal staggering of short Gaussian laser pulses. PSI at SwissFEL has made very good experience with such an approach [9] therefore we use as well their laser pulse as a reference. The above mentioned initial distribution can be generated in the ASTRA simulation code and explored for the simulations.

5.1.1 Initial bunch length

Consider a bunch of charged particles uniformly distributed in longitudinal direction with length l and with velocity $\beta = 1$ being accelerated by an RF travelling wave structure with wave length λ . Assuming that the center of the bunch has zero phase offset from the crest of the wave, the acceleration rate is decreasing and the slope is increasing as further we go away from the crest. This introduces energy spread to the bunch, which we can calculate as can be seen in Fig. 5. The length of the bunch expressed in phase of the RF is $\theta = 2\pi Tc/\lambda$. This calculation gives us good

Figure 5: *Dependence of energy spread on the initial bunch length*

estimate of what will the final energy spread be like since it is driven by the RF curvature at higher energies. However this is the theoretical minimum, realistically effects like space charge will increase the energy spread but also bunch length, which will increase the final energy spread. A good goal for the energy spread would be to have about 0.5% rms therefore we would aim for 15 ps initial bunch length or equivalent a laser duration of 15 ps. This is of course a working assumption and can be subject to change further in the development.

5.1.2 Spot size

The second important initial characteristic of the beam is its radius. Here we can't estimate with analytical calculation since space charge plays a crucial role, which must be calculated numerically. We simulated how bunches of particles with an initial bunch length of 15 ps, would evolve if we had only the RF-gun with different initial spot sizes. Here we watched three main parameters; spot size, bunch length and emittance at a distance of 0.9 m from the cathode. This distance is arbitrary chosen but near the expected position of first TWS and is there only to evaluate the effects of the space charge. As expected, the bunch always spread out in all directions. However there is a clear minimum for both spot size and emittance,

which as expected means that the lower the initial spot size is the stronger the space charge forces are and so the particles gain more positive radial momentum, increasing the spot size and emittance over time. However the intrinsic emittance at the cathode is proportional to the laser spot size. For this simplified simulations we used a fixed solenoid field around the RF-gun.

Figure 6: Spot size, emittance and bunch length at a distance of $z = 0.9$ m from the cathode as a function of the initial spot size (radius of a uniform distribution)

The results of the simulations are shown in Fig.7. From this plot we have chosen an initial beam radius of $r = 1.5$ mm. This is a bit larger radius than the minimums of the emittance but we expect additional emittance compensation during accelerations once the whole injector is optimized. For smaller spot sizes the space charge effects seem to be quite strong and we would like to avoid this regime.

5.2 Structures

5.2.1 RF-gun

The RF-gun gradient and phase will be set to $E_0 = 100\text{MV/m}$ and $\phi_0 = 0$ which is in ASTRA the phase with the maximum energy gain. These values won't be subject to change during the initial optimisation since we know that a high gradient is better for the emittance and the emittance optimum is close to the phase of maximum energy gain. Small phase changes can still be explored later on. We restricted the gradient of the RF-gun to 100 MV/m to insure a stable operation since a small emittance is not the most critical parameter for such a collider.

5.2.2 TWS

For the TWS, only the first structure's parameters are being optimised, since the others have no significant effect on the beam characteristics. We set the maximum

gradient of the TWSs to $E_0 = 25\text{MV/m}$ [6] and the phase to $\phi_0 = -2^\circ$ in order to decrease correlated energy spread introduced by space charge. Since there is no analytical estimate for the effect of the different gradients of the first TWS on the beam characteristics we used the whole range from 0 to 25 MV/m. The position of the first TWS is more important than its gradient. The optimal position depends on the emittance compensation process and therefore on the bunch charge, RF-gun gradient and the strength of the solenoid field, see the following section. For the other TW-structures the position is not very critical it will be determined by practical mechanical requirements. All other TW structures will use a gradient of 25 MV/m and on crest operation.

5.2.3 Solenoid

The first estimate for the magnetic field strength of the solenoid around the RF-gun is calculated as the strength for a given length where the particle spirals around half a circle. If there were no other effects in place, this would be too much, but since we are dealing with space charge, this proves to be a good initial estimate of the maximum field strength needed. The length of the solenoid we are using is $l = 26\text{ cm}$ since it isn't uniform we are using the FWHM value. We use a relation between the momentum of the particles, the magnetic field strength and its effective length $B_0 = \frac{\pi p}{l e}$ [10]. Since we already did some simulations, we know the average momentum of the particles is $p = 6.6\text{ MeV}/c^2$. So the initial estimate for the solenoid field strength comes down to $B_0 = 0.27\text{ T}$. We simulated the evolution of the particle bunch with previously discussed distributions, RF-gun parameters and the derived solenoid field strength. We aim to have a smooth focusing and a compensation of the defocusing transverse space charge forces with the focusing solenoid field. In order to find the right focusing for the solenoid we look at the derivative of the spot size evolution along the beam line. According to the theory of emittance compensation in photo injectors/citeemittance compensation we are looking for a minimum in the beam size and shallow divergence of the beam at the point of injection into the next accelerating structure. Therefore if we plot the spot size derivative as in Fig.7 we look for a zero crossing and a shallow slope. A good starting point for our optimisation would be therefore a field strength between $B_0 = 0.23\text{ T}$ and $B_0 = 0.24\text{ T}$ and a initial position of the first accelerating structure between 1.2 and 1.3m.

5.3 Methods of optimisation

We used two different algorithms for optimisation. As the more simple one, we treated only one parameter as variable being optimised and the other parameters were constant. This we did across the whole potential range of the parameters and spaced the parameters equidistantly. Since with this approach the computational time increases exponentially with every added parameter, we decided to only use three; longitudinal position of the first TWS, solenoid field strength and gradient of the first TWS as the set of parameters to vary. The variable was being optimised by ASTRA with the build in option of the code, to achieve the lowest emittance. For these simulation we used a low resolution set up with larger grid cells and time steps and lower number of macro-particles, then we chose the most interesting runs and

Figure 7: *Spot size derivative as a function of the bunch position. Each line corresponds to a different magnetic field strength, see legend above*

did high resolution simulation for them. This option was used primarily because it gave us an overview within a certain parameter range.

The second approach was to use a simplex based automatic algorithm developed by Bettoni for the SwissFEL [9], where we used the result from the previous simulations as an initial estimate and let the code optimise. We also added the initial spot size as a parameter to be optimized.

5.4 Results

5.4.1 Optimisation for positron production using a uniform initial distribution

First we optimised the electron beam for positron production with a bunch charge of 5.0 nC. We expect that this is the worst case scenario compared to the lower charge beam. For this case the uniform initial distribution were used and the optimisation was done with the first rather manual approach. The solenoid field and the accelerating gradient of the first structure have been varied in a certain range and the emittance and optimal longitudinal structure position has been determined. The results are summarized in Tab.6.

One can see that the gradient of the structure is not an extremely important parameter but it influences the optimal structure position and the focusing. From these results, two configurations were chosen (marked green), since they have similarly high performance. There seems to be a trade off between the position and the magnetic field. The relevant parameters are summarized in Tab.7.

E_{cav} [MV/m]	10	15	20	25
B_{sol} [T] = 0.21	10.5/0.85	11.5/0.50	12.5/0.50	
0.22	6.6/1.28	6.6/1.57	6.5/1.79	6.1/1.89
0.23	7.3/0.80	6.0/1.21	5.4/1.29	5.2/1.36
0.24	5.0/1.09	3.9/1.09	4.5/1.16	6.0/1.23

Table 6: *Manual optimisation method for a 5 nC beam with uniform distribution. Cells show the projected transverse emittance [mm mrad] and the longitudinal position of the first cavity [m].*

	Case 1	Case 2
Bunch charge	5.0 nC	5.0 nC
Initial spot size	1.5 mm	1.5 mm
Emission time [FWHM]	15 ps	15 ps
Solenoid magnetic field	0.24 T	0.23 T
Cavity gradient	15 MV/m	25 MV/m
Cavity position	1.09 m	1.36 m

Table 7: *Initial simulation parameters for the two optimised cases*

The evolution of the main beam parameters transverse emittance, energy spread, bunch length and beam size are shown in Fig.8 for both selected cases. The beam characteristics are almost similar with some difference in the beam size evolution and emittance compensation.

The longitudinal, transverse and momentum distributions of the beam at the end of the pre-injector linac are shown in Fig. 17 for both selected case. From this pictures we can see that a higher gradient (case 2) seems to result in a smoother momentum distribution since the capture efficiency into a single RF-bucket is a bit higher. Secondly it is quite visible that the transverse beam size is much larger in case (case 1) probably due to the weaker rf focusing effect and the stronger focusing around the gun. This characteristics of the beam can be of course changed by adding additional focusing.

Table 8: Evolution of critical characteristics of the beam as it travels through the beam line for two different set of parameters

Table 9: *Longitudinal, transverse and momentum distributions of the beam at the end of the pre-injector for both selected cases*

	Case 1	Case 2
Transversal emittance	2.96 mrad mm	4.05 mrad mm
Energy spread rms	760 keV	867 keV
Average energy	202 MeV	232 MeV
Beam size rms	1.38 mm	0.63 mm
Bunch length rms	1.40 mm	1.41 mm

Table 10: *Main beam characteristics at the end of the pre-injector with approximately 200 MeV average energy.*

5.4.2 Optimisation for electron production with uniform distributions and comparison of optimisation algorithms

It is expected, that the automatic algorithm performs better than the manual one, however the manual one is much less vulnerable to mistakes and doesn't need to be changed for different distribution. We assess the different performances of these two algorithms in this subsection. In order to use similar set up as with 5.0 nC beam, we decreased the initial spot size relative to the charge so that the charge density is preserved. We used the manual optimisation as described above and employed the simplex based automatic algorithm to obtain the best initial parameters. The result of the optimisation to minimise the transverse emittance is summarized in Tab.11. The main difference are in the longitudinal structure position and solenoid field strength a bit similar to the two case investigated for the 5 nC beam.

	manual	automatic
Bunch charge	3.4 nC	3.4 nC
Initial spot size	1.23 mm	1.232 mm
Emission time [FWHM]	15 ps	15 ps
Solenoid magnetic field	0.225 T	0.2413 T
Cavity gradient	15 MV/m	16.2 MV/m
Cavity position	1.47 m	1.068 m

Table 11: *Optimised initial parameters as derived by the manual and automatic optimisation*

Figure 12 shows the beam size and emittance evolution along the pre-injector as well as the final longitudinal and transverse distributions. There is not a significant difference in the two results which probably indicates that the linac setup is not extremely critical and therefore several combination of parameters can yield good results. Further simulations using the obtained distribution in the following linac should give input in how to further optimise the injector. The final beam parameters for the 3.4 nC case are summarized in Tab.13.

5.4.3 Optimising with engineering restrictions

Since both of these different charges could be generated with the same injector it would be necessary to operate with the same geometry and if possible with as many constant parameters as possible. The goal is to be able to switch within some milliseconds between the two operation modes therefore of course the position of the elements can't be changed. Phases, laser spot size and maybe magnetic fields could be potentially changed. Since the characteristics of the electron bunch for positron production are not nearly as important as the electron bunch used directly for physics collisions, we used the optimised case for 3.4 nC charge and with the above mentioned restrictions optimised again the 5.0 nC case.

From Tab. 14 and 15 we can see that even with restrictions we were able to get excellent beam parameters. This also means that we can easily change between the operations with different bunch charges by simply changing beams spot size to preserve the charge density, therefore we only need to optimise the nominal charge case and then determine the best laser parameters for positron production.

Table 12: Evolution of the beam size and emittance along the injector and longitudinal and transverse particle distributions at the end of the pre-injector linac for both optimisation methods.

	manual	automatic
Transversal emittance	3.08 mrad mm	1.94 mrad mm
Energy spread rms	642 keV	703 keV
Average energy	202 MeV	206 MeV
Beam size rms	1.01 mm	1.05 mm
Bunch length rms	1.31 mm	1.36 mm

Table 13: *Main beam characteristics at the end of the pre-injector for the 3.4 nC beam.*

Bunch charge	5.0 nC
Initial spot size	1.5 mm
Emission time [FWHM]	15 ps
Solenoid magnetic field	0.2413 T
Cavity gradient	16.2 MV/m
Cavity position	1.068 m

Table 14: *Optimised initial parameters for 5nC with fixed structure position, gradient and solenoid field*

5.4.4 Results with Gaussian distribution

As mentioned above doing simulation using a Gaussian distribution could be seen as a worst case check for our results. Changing the charge distribution in the beam fundamentally changes its behaviour, so we repeated all the steps done previously for the flat distributed beam. Here we present only the case for the nominal bunch charge of 3.4 nC since we can expect the bunch for positron production to be at similar quality as shown in the previous section. The initial beam parameters as a result of the optimisation are summarized in Tab.16.

As expected the final emittance and energy spread values are higher than with the uniform distribution by a factor two to three (see Tab.18). The longitudinal distribution is very well preserved, the transverse one, on the other hand, creates two distinct parts, center spike where most of the charge is concentrated and sparsely populated outer ring.

Transverse emittance	3.10 mrad mm
Energy spread rms	760 keV
Average energy	206 MeV
Beam size rms	0.7 mm
Bunch length rms	1.40 mm

Table 15: *Main beam characteristics at the end of the injector*

Bunch charge	3.4 nC
Initial spot size [sigma]	0.80 mm
Emission time [sigma]	4.5 ps
Solenoid magnetic field	0.245 T
Cavity gradient	10 MV/m
Cavity position	0.78 m

Table 16: *Initial beam parameters for a 3.4 nC beam with Gaussian distributions*

6 Conclusion and summary

A photo-injector based option for the electron source and pre-injector for the FCCee was studied. It turns out that such a design could be a viable option for to reliably produce the required bunch charges for electrons and for positron production. The injector could switch quickly between the different charges by adjusting the laser spot size and the solenoid magnetic field without much degradation of the beam quality. The obtained emittance and other beam parameters at the end of the pre-injector fulfil the requirements and an operation for electrons without a damping ring seems feasible. It looks like a semiconductor type cathode would be safer to use, implying a certain complexity in the cathode handling and production. The possibility to use a metal cathode will have to be investigated more. The study used ideal uniform distributions and Gaussian distributions of the initial laser pulse to study the impact of this parameter. It turns out that even a Gaussian distribution would be acceptable but with a modern laser and some effort in pulse shaping even better results should be obtainable.

In the future an alternative injector based on a simple thermionic gun will be studied due to his attraction in terms of simplicity and stability in operation. The above design needs of course to be refined as the overall FCCee injector design evolves.

Table 17: *The particle distributions at 15 m distance from the cathode with initial Gaussian distribution*

Transversal emittance	8.26 mrad mm
Energy spread rms	1102 keV
Average energy	187 MeV
Beam size rms	1.04 mm
Bunch length rms	1.61 mm

Table 18: *Main beam characteristics at the end of the injector*

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